

Dementia Care in Rural Regions: Needs and expectations from the Citizens' Perspective

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Background: The growing prevalence of dementia poses major challenges to healthcare systems, particularly in rural areas where access to specialized services is often limited. Understanding the perspectives of citizens is essential for developing care models that address regional needs effectively.

Objective: This study explores the needs and expectations regarding dementia care in a rural region in Rhineland-Palatinate, Germany. It focuses on perceived deficits in the current care infrastructure and expectations toward new small-scale dementia care models such as dementia villages to address these challenges.

Method: A total of 27 guided interviews were conducted with local stakeholders involved in dementia counseling (n = 5) and with citizens, both individually (n = 16) and within a focus group (n = 6). Participants ranged in age from 51 to 84 years (median: 65), with 22 identifying as female. Data were analysed using qualitative content analysis according to Kuckartz and Rädiker. Initial coding was performed independently by two researchers, followed by discussion and refinement of the coding system.

Outcome: Participants reported insufficient access to dementia-specific services, particularly in the areas of medical, therapeutic, and residential care. Access is often characterized by long travel distances, extended waiting times, and, in some cases, a lack of dementia-specific qualifications among healthcare professionals. Specialized facilities are rare, and people with dementia (PwD) are frequently integrated into general care settings that lack tailored support. A shortage of qualified staff and excessive bureaucratic requirements further restrict access and reduce care quality.

Citizens and stakeholders emphasized the need for decentralized, low-threshold support structures and expressed a strong preference for hybrid care models that combine residential, day, short-term, and outpatient care within a single facility. Key expectations for future care concepts include a homely, non-institutional environment, promotion of autonomy and normality, and person-centered care delivered by dementia-trained staff. Financial accessibility, proximity to relatives, access to outdoor areas, and openness to the local community were also considered important. Small-scale living units and opportunities for PwD to participate in everyday activities - such as gardening or cooking- highlighted as desirable advancements beyond traditional nursing home structures. The appropriate extent of safety-related measures was a topic of controversial discussion.

Implication for research: Current care structures in rural regions are insufficient to meet the growing demand. Innovative, small-scale care models such as dementia villages are seen as promising, but should be adapted to include hybrid service elements emphasize community integration and empowerment, reflecting regional needs and citizens' expectations.

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